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The impact of modern varieties on rice production and farmers' income in Laos

S. Shrestha, IRRI; K. Goeppert, Lao-IRRI Project, Vientiane, Lao PDR; M.A. Bell, IRRI; and K. Douangvila, Lao-IRRI Project, Vientiane

The rice production systems of the Lao PDR have undergone dramatic changes in the last decade. These changes include cultivation of rice in the dry season and widespread adoption of modern rice varieties (MVs). These factors have contributed to a 53% increase in production—from 1.5 million t in 1990 to 2.3 million t in 2001—or an annual increase in rice production of almost 5%. These increases have enabled the Lao PDR to attain national self-sufficiency in rice despite a high (2.7% y^{-1}) population growth rate (Shrestha 2002).

The Lao-IRRI Research and Training Project, established in 1990, was a catalyst for increasing rice production in Laos during the 1990s. The goal of the project was to assist the government of Laos in increasing rice production to achieve self-sufficiency on a sustainable basis. It had the broad-based mandate to improve rice production systems by undertaking research and to enhance the skills of the national scientists to support and undertake such activities. These activities were undertaken in collaboration with the Lao National Rice Research Program (NRRP). In a short period, technology packages were developed, consisting of 10 Lao modern rice varieties (LMVs) with improved crop management practices. The project also recommended the use of other modern varieties (OMVs) such as the Thai-improved RD varieties available from across the border (Lao-IRRI 2000). To assess the farm-level impact of these varieties and technology packages, a

survey was conducted in three main rice-producing regions (Champassak and Savannakhet provinces, Vientiane Municipality) in April 2002. The results presented here are based on national-level data and the farm survey. In all, 240 households—with 80 households from each region—were surveyed.

Adoption of MVs

Modern varieties were planted on 81% of the rice area surveyed. All rice area in the dry season and 74% of the wet-season rice area were planted to MVs (Table 1). The LMVs dominate in the dry season.

Yield difference

Both the LMVs and OMVs substantially outyielded the traditional varieties (TVs), while the LMVs outyielded the OMVs (Table 2). LMVs have 66% more yield than TVs. The yield advantage of LMVs over OMVs is 24%.

Table 1. Area planted to traditional and different types of modern varieties.

Variety type ^a	Percentage of rice area		
	Wet season	Dry season	Total
Lao-IRRI MVs	29.4	59.9	35.8
Other MVs	46.1	40.1	44.8
Total MVs	75.5	100.0	80.6
TVs	24.5	—	19.4
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0

^aMVs = modern varieties, TVs = traditional varieties.
Data source: Field survey 2002.

Table 2. Percentage difference in yield between traditional and modern varieties.

Region	OMVs/TVs	LMVs/TVs	LMVs/OMVs
Champassak	20.5	42.2	18.0
Savannakhet	22.2	54.2	26.2
Vientiane	71.0	102.1	18.2
Three regions	37.9	66.2	20.8

TVs = traditional varieties, OMVs = other modern varieties, LMVs = Lao-IRRI modern varieties.

Table 3. Farm household budget (\$ ha⁻¹).

	TVs	OMVs	LMVs	% increase in production value		
				LMVs/TVs	OMVs/TVs	LMVs/OMVs
Gross value	280.3	332.4	394.6	40.8	18.6	18.7
Paid out cost	19.6	53.7	72.9	271.1	173.4	35.7
Net value	260.7	278.7	321.7	23.4	6.9	15.4

TVs = traditional varieties, OMVs = other modern varieties, LMVs = Lao-IRRI modern varieties.

Difference in farmers' income

Costs and returns associated with different categories of rice varieties are presented in Table 3. The net return of LMVs is the highest despite the increased cost of production. Farmers' net income increased by 23% with the adoption of LMVs, representing an increase of \$75 ha⁻¹. With the adoption of OMVs, farmers' income increased by only \$19 ha⁻¹. The farmers who grew LMVs were able to obtain an additional income of about \$56 ha⁻¹ relative to those who grew OMVs.

The lowland rice area in Laos in 2001 was 588,000 ha. Using the adoption rate of LMVs estimated earlier (36%), the total increase in farmers' income relative to the TVs is thus estimated to be \$16 million y⁻¹.

References

- Lao-IRRI Project. 2000. Rice varieties: recommendations for the wet-season lowland environment of the Lao PDR. Vientiane (Lao PDR): Lao-IRRI Project.
- Shrestha S. 2002. Consultancy report on the impact of the Lao-IRRI project. Vientiane (Lao PDR): Lao-IRRI Project.